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Review Article

**PRADER-WILLI SYNDROME REVIEW AND ANALYSIS:
SYSTEMATIC REVIEW IN LITERATURE****Ahmed Alsharhan^{1*}, Lujain Abdu², Rawan Alsafh³, Dania Alibrahim³, Abdullah Alraqi⁴,
Asalh Saeedi², Hatun Shualuwalah², Ahmed Alanazi⁴, Ghadeer Surrati³, Duaa Alahmadi³**¹Imam Mohammed Bin Saud Islamic University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia²King AbdulAziz University, jeddah, Saudi Arabia³Batterjee Medical College, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia⁴Jordan University of Science and Technology, Al-Ramtha, Irbid, Jordan**Abstract:**

This review is aiming to review and analysis the Prader -Willi Syndrome. The present review was conducted by searching in Medline, Embase, Web of Science, Science Direct, BMJ journal and Google Scholar for, researches, review articles and reports, published over the past years. Books published on the Prader-Willi Syndrome. If several studies had similar findings, we randomly selected one or two to avoid repetitive results. Based on findings and results this review found. The studies provided evidence that absolute TEE, REE, SEE, and AEE are lower in individuals with PWS than in age-, sex-, and body mass index-matched individuals without the syndrome. Alterations in lean body mass and lower physical activity amounts appear to be responsible for the lower energy expenditure in PWS rather than metabolic differences. Regardless of the underlying mechanism for lower TEE, the estimation of energy requirements with the use of equations derived for the general population would result in weight gain in individuals with PWS. The determination of energy requirements for weight management in individuals with PWS requires a more comprehensive understanding of energy metabolism. Future studies should aim to comprehensively profile all specific components of energy expenditure in individuals with PWS with the use of appropriately matched controls and gold standard methods to measure energy metabolism and body composition

Keywords: Prader-Willi syndrome, energy metabolism, resting energy expenditure, activity energy expenditure.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Ahmed Alsharhan,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Prader-Willi syndrome (PWS) is a genetic disorder due to loss of function of specific genes.¹ In newborns symptoms include weak muscles, poor feeding, and slow development.¹ Beginning in childhood the person becomes constantly hungry which often leads to obesity and type 2 diabetes.¹ There is also typically mild to moderate intellectual impairment and behavioral problems.¹ Often the forehead is narrow, hands and feet small, height short, skin light in color, and those affected are unable to have children [1].

About 74% of cases occur when part of the father's chromosome 15 is deleted.¹ In another 25% of cases the person has two copies of chromosome 15 from their mother and none from their father. As parts of the chromosome from the mother are turned off they end up with no working copies of certain genes [1]. PWS is not generally inherited but instead the genetic changes happen during the formation of the egg, sperm, or in early development. There are no known risk factors [2]. Those who have one child with PWS have less than a 1% chance of the next child being affected [2]. A similar mechanism occurs in Angelman syndrome except there is a defective chromosome 15 from the mother or two copies from the father [3].

METHODS:

The present review was conducted November 2018 in accordance with the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) declaration standards for systematic reviews. We reviewed all the topics on Pediatric hydrocephalus Management, such as, etiology, epidemiology, and clinical statistics. To achieve this goal, we searched Medline, Embase, Web of Science, Science Direct, and Google Scholar for, researches, review articles and reports, published over the past 15 years. Books published on Pediatric hydrocephalus Management. Our search was completed without language restrictions. Then we extracted data on study year, study design, and key outcome on Prader-Willi Syndrome. The selected studies were summarized and unreproducible studies were excluded. Selected data is shown in the Table 1.

Inclusion criteria

Studies were included in this review if energy expenditure in individuals with PWS was compared with matched controls and energy expenditure was measured in both groups with the use of indirect calorimetry (IC) or doubly labeled water (DLW).

Exclusion criteria

Irrelevant articles [not related to the aim of this review and articles that did not meet the inclusion criteria in this review.

Data extraction and analysis

Information relating to each of the systematic review elements was extracted from the studies and collated in qualitative tables. Direct analysis of the studies of Prader-Willi Syndrome is made with extreme caution, as different sampling techniques can provide bias as overview of the assemblage.

RESULTS:

The criteria for the decision to treat were quite variable among different institutions and different study groups.

The mechanism of action for the significant overall reduction in energy expenditure in individuals with PWS is likely multifactorial. Approximately one-third of children with PWS have hypothyroidism due to hypothalamic-pituitary dysfunction, resulting in low or low-normal concentrations of thyroid-stimulating hormone and low concentrations of total or free thyroxine. Therefore, central hypothyroidism may play a role in the reduced energy expenditure demonstrated in children with PWS [4]. A PWS mouse model [mice lacking MAGE-like 2 (Magel2)] demonstrated normal leptin sensitivity in proopiomelanocortin neurons into the early post weaning period; however, thereafter, the mice demonstrated progressive leptin insensitivity, which is predicted to impair the release of the melanocortin receptor agonist α -melanocyte stimulating hormone, with downstream effects to reduce energy expenditure⁵. It is speculated that a similar reduction in leptin responsiveness occurs over time in children with PWS; this would account for a reduction in energy expenditure in individuals with PWS, which would worsen with aging. Previous research has examined whether individuals with PWS exhibit reduced fat oxidation. One study by PurteLL et al [6]. did not detect metabolic defect in respiratory quotient or fat oxidation in individuals with PWS after a mixed high-carbohydrate and high-fat meal. However, Rubin et al [7], examined the effect of PWS on the hormonal and metabolic response to resistance exercise; individuals with PWS demonstrated earlier increases in FAs during recovery and exhibited higher glycerol and ketone concentrations than controls, suggesting incomplete fat oxidation⁷. Previous longitudinal studies in Pima Indians report that low fat oxidizers (90th percentile

for respiratory quotient) had a 2.5 times greater risk of gaining ≥ 5 kg of body weight than high fat oxidizers⁸. Furthermore, those successful at maintaining weight loss tend to have higher fat oxidation rates than those experiencing weight relapse [9]. Thus, lower fat oxidation in individuals with PWS might also contribute to the imbalance between intake and energy expenditure. Finally, lower spontaneous physical activity and sympathetic activity have been reported in individuals with PWS. [10] Children with PWS demonstrated no exercise-induced increase in catecholamines and an ~40%

lower heart rate elevation in response to exercise compared with controls. These findings suggest a sympathetic autonomic deficit in PWS [11]. In summary, altered endocrine function (thyroid and leptin deficits) and lower fat oxidation, sympathetic activity, and spontaneous physical activity are multiple factors that might play an etiologic role in the reduction in energy expenditure that is characteristic of individuals with PWS. Further longitudinal studies are required to determine if this defect in energy expenditure progressively worsens with age.

Table (1) Results from Sequencing Studies.

Authors	Study design and purpose	Study population	Main Results
Bekx et al., 2003 ¹²	Cross-sectional study to evaluate BC in relation to energy expenditure in infants and toddlers with PWS	PWS, n = 16, 8 F/8 M Age, mo: 12.4 \pm 6	Absolute TEE compared with published normative data: 24% lower in PWS Rates for PWS subjects comparable with published normative data
Butler et al., 2007 ¹⁰	Cross-sectional study to determine the relations among body composition, activity amounts, and metabolic rates	PWS, n = 48; 27 F/21 M Age, y: 23 \pm 9	TEE compared with controls: 20% lower in PWS subjects, kcal/8 h, unadjusted; lower with adjustment for FM; no difference with adjustment for LBM 16% lower in PWS subjects, kcal/min; lower with adjustment for FM; no difference with adjustments for LBM or BW
Lloret-Linares et al., 2013 ¹³	Cross-sectional study to compare REE of adults with PWS or lesional genetic hypothalamic obesity with obese controls	PWS, n = 16 F Age, y: 25.8 \pm 4.9	Absolute REE compared with controls: Female PWS subjects had rates similar to controls and subjects with HD, unadjusted; when adjusted for age, PWS subjects had 13% higher rates than controls and similar rates to HD subjects when adjusted for LBM Male PWS subjects had 19% lower rates than controls and similar rates to HD subjects, unadjusted; no differences when adjusted for age and LBM
Purtell et al., 2015 ⁶	Cross-sectional study to measure changes in energy expenditure in response to meals	PWS, n = 11, 4 F/7 M Age, y: 27.5 \pm 2.7	Rates for PWS subjects were comparable with those of obese and lean controls, unadjusted; no differences when adjusted for FFM and FM Rates for PWS subjects were comparable with those of obese and lean controls, unadjusted; no differences when adjusted for FFM and FM
Goldstone et al., 2002 ¹⁴	Cross-sectional study to assess REE	PWS, n = 8 F	8% lower in PWS subjects than in obese controls, unadjusted; lower after adjustment for age, height, and weight and after adjustment for age and FM; higher after adjustment for age and FFM; no difference after adjustment for age, FFM, and FM

DISCUSSION:

From the literature to date, the findings suggest that PWS individuals have lower absolute energy expenditure than age-, sex-, and BMI-matched controls because of reduced REE, SEE, and AEE; these differences may be secondary to altered body composition and hormone dysfunction. However, due to the paucity of information on DIT in individuals with PWS, the relative contribution of specific components of TEE to the altered metabolism in PWS is not clear. Once body composition is taken into consideration, many differences disappear, suggesting that there might in fact be no overall disturbance in whole-body energy metabolism. However, these results should be interpreted with caution because of the inherent limitations in the use of adjustment methods and the discrepancies in the methods used to measure body composition in PWS. Additionally, DIT needs to be assessed in individuals with PWS and compared with healthy obese individuals, whereas differences in energy expenditure estimates according to genetic subtype and impact of hormonal therapies need further study.

CONCLUSIONS:

Finally, it is important to highlight that although no metabolic differences have been documented to date, accurate assessments of FM and FFM could certainly affect the calculation of energy requirements for those with PWS compared with healthy controls. Currently, energy requirements are based on predictive equations used to assess REE. These equations incorporate the use of body weight and assume a "healthy or reference" body composition, which is problematic in a clinical cohort in which disturbances in body composition have been clearly documented. The abnormal body composition in individuals with PWS (characterized by reduced FFM and increased FM) would lower energy expenditure and thus lower energy requirements compared with healthy individuals. Thus, assessing body composition accurately with the use of a valid techniques and determining energy requirements taking body composition into consideration are integral parts of dietary management in individuals with PWS. Increasing FFM and maximizing physical activity should be considered to increase energy expenditure in PWS.

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Abbreviations used in this paper: AEE, BEE, REE, and TEE values are expressed as kcal/d unless otherwise indicated. AEE, activity energy expenditure; BC, body composition; BEE, basal energy expenditure; BIA, bioelectrical impedance analysis; BMR, basal metabolic rate; BW, body weight; DEL, deletion; DLW, doubly labeled water; F, female; FFM, fat-free mass; FM, fat mass; GH, growth hormone; HD, hypothalamic damage; IC, indirect calorimetric; ID, imprinting center defects, LBM, lean body mass; M, male; PWS, Prader-Willi syndrome; REE, resting energy expenditure; ref., reference; SEE, sleeping energy expenditure; TEE, total energy expenditure; UPD, uniparental disomy.